

A MULTISCALE DAMAGE INITIATION MODEL FOR CNT-ENHANCED EPOXY POLYMERS

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ABSTRACT

A multiscale methodology that accurately simulates the inelastic behavior of epoxy polymers initiating at the molecular level due to bond elongation and subsequent bond dissociation is presented in this paper. The system investigated in this study comprises a combination of crystalline carbon nanotubes (CNTs) dispersed in amorphous epoxy polymer molecules. Molecular dynamics (MD) simulations are performed with an appropriate bond order based force field to capture deformation-induced bond dissociation between atoms within the simulation volume. In order to overcome the influence of thermal vibrations of bonds on bond dissociation energy (BDE), a quasi-continuum (QC) approach, excluding the effects of temperature, is explored. Results indicate that a QC approach can simulate bond breakage leading to brittle behavior in amorphous epoxy polymer. The novel combination of MD deformation tests with high strain rates at near-zero temperatures, however, is seen to provide a more computationally efficient alternative for the study of bond dissociation phenomenon in amorphous epoxy polymer. The corresponding BDE extracted from the simulation volume is used as input to the continuum damage mechanics (CDM) model to study matrix failure at the microscale. The material parameters for the CDM model are directly obtained from physics-based atomistic simulations, thus, significantly reducing the propagation of errors in the multiscale framework.

1 INTRODUCTION

Nanocomposites consisting of inorganic/organic nanoparticles dispersed in a polymer medium offer improved performance and are emerging as one of the most promising areas in materials research with potential benefits for numerous applications. However, despite the enormous advantages offered by these materials, their implementation remains limited due to a lack of clear understanding of the basic relationships between the nanoscale physical and chemical parameters, and macroscale properties. To model the behavior of polymeric systems integrated with nanoparticles, several computational approaches have been developed [1, 2], such as homogenization techniques, molecular dynamics (MD) simulation, Monte Carlo (MC) simulation and the Mori-Tanaka approach. MD simulations, which study the interactions among a group of atoms or molecules, have been widely employed to gain insights on the formation and dissociation of cross-link bonds in polymers with appropriate force field potentials [3]. Koo et al. [4] recently introduced a stochastic approach to simulate the chemical curing process in epoxy polymers through MD simulations that utilize a cutoff distance to decide bond formation. Subramanian et al. [5] studied the effect of the polymer cross-linking density on the linear elastic mechanical properties of a CNT-epoxy polymer system. A review of modeling techniques for determining the mechanical properties of polymeric nanocomposites using MD and MC methods has been presented by Valavala and Odegard [6].

Although the linear elastic response of carbon nanotube (CNT)-enhanced epoxy polymers has been extensively studied [3-6], fundamental behavior at the molecular level that causes inelastic response of the nanocomposite material is still not well understood. Amorphous polymers at temperatures well below their glass transition temperature ($T \ll T_g$) exhibit brittle behavior, whereas semicrystalline polymers tend to exhibit ductile behavior prior to failure at temperatures that fall between melting and glass transition ($T_m < T < T_g$), thus clearly demonstrating the different mechanisms of damage initiation in crystalline and amorphous materials. Mott and co-workers [7] used an atomistic model to

simulate plastic deformation in glassy polymers. The model accounted for bonded and non-bonded interactions among atoms and also investigated the segmental motions in the polymer chain that causes plastic flow leading to fully developed plastic events in the molecular system. A pioneering study was undertaken by Rottler et al. [8] employing molecular simulations to calculate the macroscopic fracture energy of glassy polymers through crazing and cracking. The study investigated the elastic properties of bundles of polymer chains ahead of a crack tip by simulating a tensile deformation to stretch these molecular chains, and thereby inducing bond breakage. A simple continuum approach was used here to estimate the work required to craze the material ahead of the crack tip in the process zone. Rottler and Robbins [9] also implemented coarse-grain MD simulations to investigate failure by bond dissociation occurring between glassy polymer adhesives and a substrate. Another study by Rottler [10] related macroscopic phenomena such as physical aging, strain hardening, and fracture to molecular level events using coarse-grain MD. These studies reveal that craze formation is one of the major sources of toughness in glassy polymers, and bond dissociation subsequent to crazing leads to nucleation of local defects at higher length scales. However, accurate simulation of the brittle behavior arising from successive bond dissociation in amorphous epoxy polymers containing crystalline nanoparticles at the atomistic length scale has yet to be addressed.

To model strain softening and subsequent material degradation leading to damage at the microscale, several approaches have been explored to date. de Borst and Sluys [11] computed the width of a finite plastic localization zone and the corresponding dissipation energy for an elasto-plastic, strain softening Cosserat continuum. The study incorporated a von Mises plasticity model formulated within the framework of a Cosserat continuum. Sayers and Kachanov [12] developed an approach to estimate the elastic stiffness tensor for an arbitrary orientation distribution of cracks at finite crack densities. Their approach relies on a tensorial transformation of the effective elastic constants for isotropic orientation statistics through the use of a second-order crack density tensor. Recent studies have shown the successful implementation of a continuum damage mechanics (CDM) model within a simple multiscale framework [13, 14] for composite materials, especially to examine matrix failure. However, most of the studies detailed here use homogenization approximations, such as the Mori-Tanaka method, to estimate the effective degraded material properties at damage sites.

In this paper, a hybrid force field MD simulation methodology is adopted to form cross-link bonds between the resin and the hardener molecules in the presence of CNTs, and to simulate damage initiation. The effect of thermal vibration of bonds on the strain applied at the nanoscale is investigated, following which the bond vibration frequency of a few individual bonds are calculated from the simulations. The correlation between temperature and strain rate employed in MD simulations and the corresponding variations in potential energy observed in the epoxy polymer system during post-yield deformation are also addressed. The quasi-continuum (QC) approach is a widely accepted technique for estimating the long-term spatial and temporal average of the atomic virial stresses, which eventually converges to the value of the continuum Cauchy stress [15]. However, QC simulations are computationally intensive and time consuming. This paper presents an alternative to simulation of damage caused by successive bond breakages; it demonstrates a method whereby a combination of high strain rate and low temperature MD simulations can be used to better understand damage initiation. The dissipated energy due to bond breakage calculated at the atomistic level is used to develop a material parameter that defines damage at the continuum level. This material parameter describes the degree of damage in various sections of the epoxy polymer in the form of a new constituent with degraded material properties; hence, this continuum approach simulates damage in an explicit manner at the microscale. This multiscale framework integrating a computationally efficient numerical approximation to a physics-based damage initiation phenomenon and a continuum damage mechanics model provides valuable insights into damage precursor and performance of nanopolymers.

2 MOLECULAR MODEL

The molecular structures of the epoxy resin and the hardener that constitute the polymer used in this study are Di-Glycidyl Ether of Bisphenol F (DGEBF) and Di-Ethylene Tri-Amine (DETA), respectively. The MD simulation package, Large-scale Atomic Molecular Massively Parallel Simulator (LAMMPS) [16], is used to perform the simulations. Two all-atom force fields, OPLS

(Optimized Potentials for Liquid Simulations) for CNTs [17] and MMFF (Merck Molecular Force Field) for the epoxy polymer [18], are implemented to obtain the atomic and molecular interactions in the elastic region. A stochastic cross-link formation approach, based on a cutoff value for covalent bond formation between active sites is adopted to simulate the epoxy curing process [4]. The probability distribution of cross-linking degree for the polymer system and the variation of mechanical properties with cross-linking degree has been characterized in a previous work by the author [5].

Traditional MD simulations employed with an empirical force field are not capable of capturing bond dissociation between atoms leading to plasticity. Although MD simulations that employ an empirical force field are useful to study processes in a system around its equilibrium state (e.g., curing), they are not appropriate for investigating covalent bond dissociation occurring away from the equilibrium state (e.g., during deformation tests). Classical force fields show an asymptotic increase in bond energy with elongation of bonds, whereas a bond order based force field is capable of capturing bond breakage beyond a critical bond length by stabilizing the energy curve. The external forces applied during a deformation test propagate through bonds in the matrix and in turn, the deformation induced by mechanical loading elongates covalent bonds. It is, therefore, of interest to capture the effective local force in the deformed thermoset matrix in order to identify covalent bond dissociation, which characterizes the plasticity in the system at higher length scales. Hence, a bond order based potential is introduced to capture bond elongation and subsequent dissociation of covalent bonds.

The identification of optimal parameters for the bond order based potential that can accurately characterize the nonlinear response of nanopolymers requires rigorous calculations involving density functional theory (DFT) arising from quantum mechanics. There are several bond order based potentials that exist for organic systems and hydrocarbons [19-23]. The most appropriate bond order based potential for the CNT-enhanced polymer system under consideration is determined by a bond elongation test of a specific C-H bond in a CNT with end-Hydrogen atoms followed by the estimation of the corresponding bond dissociation energy (BDE) from MD simulations. The BDE calculated from MD simulations using different potentials is compared to the bond strength of the C-H bond in CNTs reported in literature. The bond strength of the C-H bond in CNTs was calculated using DFT to be -2.39 eV (equivalent to -55.11 kCal/mol) as reported by Wei et al. [24]. Table 1 presents the bond dissociation energy calculated from MD simulations using different bond order based potential parameters. Based on the values in Table 1, the force field parameters reported by Singh and co-workers shows the best correlation with DFT results and will be employed in all the deformation simulations using a bond order based potential.

Bond order based potential	BDE (kCal/mol)
Chenoweth et al. [18]	-86.45
Weismiller et al. [19]	-89.66
Singh et al. [20]	-57.04
Mattsson et al. [21]	-145.22

Table 1: Comparison of bond dissociation energy

3 THERMAL VIBRATION OF BONDS

The application of temperature to a molecular system excites the system and causes the atoms to vibrate about their mean positions. The increase in temperature leads to an increase in the amplitude of molecular vibrations. In polymers, thermal degradation occurs when the energy of vibration exceeds the primary bonding between atoms, while the transitional phenomena associated with glass transition are related to rotation and vibration of molecular chains [25]. The frequency of vibration of a bond is directly proportional to its strength. For e.g., a C-C bond has a lower bond vibration frequency than a C-H bond. The higher the bond vibration frequency, the higher the energy required for breaking the bond. During the atomistic simulation of a deformation test, incremental strains are applied to deform the simulation volume, following which the atoms in the volume get remapped to new positions at each time step. This deformation of the simulation volume and subsequent remapping of atoms causes the bond length between atoms to vary based on the local force experienced by the atoms; however,

the bond length is re-equilibrated between time steps due to thermal vibration. This re-equilibration occurs because the frequency of bond vibrations is much higher than the rate at which the strain is applied on the simulation volume. Therefore, in order to efficiently simulate bond elongation and dissociation between atoms, the effect of thermal vibration needs to be decoupled from the mechanical strain imparted to the simulation volume. It is important to note that the strain in the simulation volume is not equal to the macroscopic strain observed during a deformation test.

A bond vibration frequency analysis is performed on several bonds in the constituent molecules of the system. In order to calculate the bond vibration frequency, the molecular system is equilibrated in an NPT ensemble for 100 ps at 300 K and 1 atm. The fluctuation in bond length for the bond of interest about its equilibrium value is plotted with time, and the data is mapped to the frequency domain using fast Fourier transform (FFT). The peak value of frequency determines the primary vibration frequency of the corresponding bond. Since the molecular system is at a near-equilibrium state throughout the equilibration, MD simulations with an empirical force field can be used to extract the bond vibration frequency. The bond stretching vibration frequency calculated for a carbon-carbon double bond (C=C) using FFT is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Bond stretching vibration frequency for C=C bond in ethene

The C=C bond vibration frequency in ethene calculated from the aforementioned technique is 51.56 THz. This technique to calculate the bond stretching vibration frequency from bond length variation during equilibration is validated by comparing the frequency value to spectroscopy data published in the literature. Based on the results from spectroscopy, the C=C bond frequency in ethane was found to be ~49.5 THz [26]. The bond stretching vibration frequency analysis is further extended to specific bonds in the CNT-epoxy system and the results are summarized in Table 2. The calculation of bond stretching vibration frequency provides better insight into thermally induced vibration in the system. In the following sections, the values of bond vibration frequency will be used as a guideline to develop a computationally efficient numerical framework to simulate bond breakage in the CNT-polymer system.

Bond type	Bond stretching vibration frequency (THz)
C=C (sp ² , CNT)	21.48
C-H (sp ³ , CNT)	63.48
C-C (benzene ring, resin)	33.45
C-O (resin)	38

Table 2: Bond stretching vibrational frequency at 300 K for various bonds in the unit cell

4 FRACTURE AT THE ATOMIC SCALE

The importance of atomic scale effects on microscopic fracture has been well recognized over the past few decades, yet the focus of even recent research has been limited to the understanding of atomic scale fracture in crystalline lattice-based material systems such as metals [27], and graphene [28]. Karger-Kocsis [29] provided an analytical formulation to study the influence of fundamental molecular variables on the essential work to fracture in amorphous polymers; however, the essential work to fracture was not quantified using a discrete molecular model. In order to relate discrete atomic level parameters to a continuum phenomenon called fracture, QC approaches that assume an embedded atomistic crack tip in a bulk continuum material have been widely adopted. The QC method for crystalline materials is founded on the Cauchy-Born approximation, a hypothesis that relates the movement of atoms in the crystal lattice to the overall deformation in a bulk solid. Thus, the QC method serves as a mapping technique for strain from the continuum mechanics framework to the discrete atomic framework. This assumption, however, is not appropriate for amorphous material systems, and the displacement of atoms does not follow the overall deformation in the bulk solid. Instead, the local force experienced by atom clusters dictates the motion and displacement of individual atoms and molecules in amorphous solids.

4.1 Quasi-continuum integrated MD simulation

In the LAMMPS framework, the QC code based on the concepts presented by Tadmor et al. [30] simulates quasi-static loading at zero temperature and uses energy minimization to find equilibrium configurations at each strain step. The simulation volume is deformed using the ‘change_box’ command; the atom coordinates in the volume are remapped from a previously stored box shape/size to a new one using an affine transformation [31, 32]. The method is also able to simulate an absolute zero temperature condition in the atomic system thereby discarding all the effects of thermal vibration of bonds. Thus, the QC method is appropriate for investigating bond elongation and bond breakage in an MD simulation due to pure mechanical loading. However, the energy minimization associated with each strain step makes the method computationally intensive and time-consuming. A CNT-epoxy unit cell with 25,700 atoms is constructed and the QC method is applied to the unit cell for 1000 tensile strain steps resulting in 50% final strain. The QC integrated MD simulation is performed on a computing node with Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU E5-2640 v2 @ 2.00GHz processors using eight CPU cores and the total wall clock time for a single simulation was well over 100 hours. The prohibitively large computational time associated with QC integrated MD simulations warrants a numerical framework that can simulate fracture in amorphous solids in a reliable and computationally efficient manner.

4.2 Alternative approach to capture bond dissociation

The addition of heat increases the amplitude of vibration of atoms and the kinetic energy also causes the atomic bonds to stretch and relax about their equilibrium lengths. Table 3 shows the reduction in bond vibration frequency obtained from MD simulations performed on the unit cell at near-zero temperature.

Bond type	Bond vibration frequency (THz)	
	300 K	~0 K
C-C (benzene ring, resin)	33.45	0.8
C-O (resin)	38	0.7

Table 3: Comparison of bond vibration frequencies at different temperatures

In order to mitigate the influence of bond vibration on bond elongation in amorphous materials, and to provide an alternative to the computationally intensive QC method, two approaches are explored in this paper. The first approach implements MD simulation with hybrid force fields (empirical force field for equilibration and curing, and bond order based force field for deformation and bond breakage) at near-zero temperatures. The second approach uses MD simulation to perform deformation tests at

extremely high strain rates. These strain rates are higher than the average bond vibration frequency; hence, the application of successive strain steps occurs faster than bond vibrations, and thus, thermal effects cannot re-equilibrate the lengths of bonds in the system.

A tensile deformation simulation is performed on a unit cell with 3% CNT by weight (total 26,000 atoms). An absolute zero temperature condition leads to zero kinetic energy, and the atoms in the system cannot move; therefore, MD simulations are not possible at zero temperature. Here, subsequent to the equilibration of the system for 100 ps at near-zero temperature (~ 1 K), a tensile deformation is performed until 100% strain and the corresponding temperature value and variation in potential energy resulting from elongation, distortion, and dissociation of bonds is calculated at each strain step. Figures 2(a) and (b) illustrate the variation in temperature and potential energy during the tensile deformation simulation performed at different strain rates ranging from $1 \times 10^9 \text{ s}^{-1}$ to $1 \times 10^{12} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

Figure 2: (a) Temperature variation during tensile deformation at different strain rates
(b) Potential energy variation during tensile deformation at different strain rates

The temperature at the end of the equilibration stage is calculated to be 1.86 K, following which the tensile deformation is applied on the simulation volume at different strain rates. For higher strain rate cases, the fluctuation of temperature during the application of strain is higher. This high fluctuation is because the magnitude of applied perturbation (strain, in this case) from the equilibrium state is larger for high strain rate simulations. Thus, low strain rate simulations with a lower magnitude of perturbation, and a longer run time maintain a value of temperature close to the target temperature, whereas high strain rate cases are only able to achieve a stable temperature of 5.89 K. Typically, an increase in temperature is expected to raise the kinetic energy of the system; however, the kinetic energy induced in the system could lead to multiple modes of vibration such as bond stretching, bond angle bending, and bond dihedral and bond improper torsion. These geometric changes could increase the potential energy of the system, although this change may not be as significant as the change in kinetic energy.

In order to quantify the effect of temperature on potential energy variations caused by geometric distortions, MD simulations were performed with equilibration at two different temperatures – 1 K and 100 K. The tensile deformations were applied at multiple strain rates at these two temperatures. Figures 3(a) – (d) show the variation of potential energy with strain at different strain rates ranging from 1×10^{10} to 2×10^{13} .

Figure 3: Effect of temperature on potential energy at strain rate
(a) 1×10^{10} (b) 1×10^{12} (c) 1×10^{13} (d) 2×10^{13}

The plots illustrate that the systems that were equilibrated at a higher temperature possess higher potential energy during the initial steps of the tensile test although the simulation volume was constructed with the same initial configuration of molecules. This phenomenon is seen to be true at all strain rates that were applied. The variation in potential energy due to increase in the average temperature of the molecular system confirms the hypothesis that temperature indirectly contributes to an increase in potential energy by causing geometric bond distortions as a result of atomic vibrations. The trends observed from Figures 3(a) – (d) indicate the interplay of two important phenomena causing variation in potential energy: case (i) the increase in temperature causes geometric distortions in the molecular system and indirectly leads to an increase in potential energy, and case (ii) the application of strain to the simulation volume leads to bond elongation and a corresponding increase in potential energy. Depending on the values of temperature and the applied strain rate, one of these phenomena dominates over the other.

In Figure 3(a), the applied strain rate is less than the value of bond stretching vibration frequencies at 0 K and 100 K; therefore, case (i) dominates in this range of strain rate. In Figure 3(b), the applied strain rate is higher than bond vibration frequencies at 0 K but lower than the bond vibration frequencies at 100 K. This indicates that case (ii) is dominant in the 0 K simulations whereas case (i) plays a more important role in the 100 K simulation. At higher strain rates ($\sim 10^{13}$), as shown in Figures 3(c) and (d), the effect of temperature difference is reduced significantly because the applied strain rate is higher than the bond vibrational frequencies in the 0 K and the 100 K simulations (see Table 3). If the strain rate of the deformation is faster than the bond stretching vibration, the effect of re-equilibration of the stretched bond due to thermal vibration is reduced. Therefore, the applied strain is transferred completely to the atomic bonds and case (ii) dominates over case (i). Figure 3(d) shows

that the potential energy values almost converge in spite of the difference in temperature, indicating that the potential energy is invariant to temperature at high strain rates. Thus, the effects of temperature on the deformation test are reduced at high strain rates, and the variation in potential energy can be fully attributed to the increase in strain in the system causing bond elongation and bond dissociation. Simulations to model bond dissociation in amorphous polymers can now be performed even at finite temperatures without a computationally intensive QC method. The variation of bond energy between the undeformed, unbound state of the molecular system and at each time step of the deformation test is used to quantify the BDE. The microscale continuum damage model utilizes the BDE quantified for polymer systems with various CNT weight fractions as input to define the damage parameter.

5 CDM INTEGRATED STOCHASTIC MICROSACLE MODEL

The matrix damage and failure model at the continuum level utilizes the CDM formulation empowered by the integration of atomistically obtained BDE density. The BDE density due to bond breakage in the simulation volume calculated at the nanoscale is used to define a material parameter for damage at the continuum level. This material parameter transforms the damaged material in the continuum simulation to a new constituent with altered material properties; hence, this methodology addresses the deficiencies posed by fracture mechanics frameworks encountering elastic constitutive relations under singularity conditions. The multiscale CDM approach also makes computation in an FEA framework convenient as the need to develop exclusive damage elements, such as in extended FEM (XFEM), is averted.

It is well established that the fundamental cause of plastic behavior in amorphous polymer is the elongation and subsequent breakage of covalent bonds. Hence, the variation in bond energy under deformation can be directly related to plastic deformation at the higher length scales. Figure 4 illustrates the variation of BDE density with CNT weight fraction in the polymer matrix, for different strains, during the deformation test. The effects of the addition of CNTs in the epoxy matrix on the overall elastic and inelastic mechanical response of the nanocomposite are discussed in Ref [5].

Figure 4: Variation of BDE density with CNT weight fraction and strain

From the BDE density quantified at the molecular level, a nonlinear curve fitting method is adopted to obtain a mathematical relationship between BDE density, CNT weight fraction in the epoxy matrix, and applied strain as described in Equation 1, where B is the BDE density calculated from MD simulations, ρ is the weight fraction of CNT, and ϵ is the strain.

$$B(\epsilon, \rho) = (a\rho^3 + b\rho^2 + c\rho + d)\epsilon^3 + (e\rho^3 + f\rho^2 + g\rho + h)\epsilon^2 + (i\rho^3 + j\rho^2 + k\rho + l)\epsilon \quad (1)$$

A damage parameter d is formulated to define and quantify material degradation as follows.

$$d = \frac{B(\epsilon, \rho) - B_{ip}}{B_c - B_{ip}} \quad (2)$$

B_c , in Equation 2, represents the critical value of BDE density at which the material loses load carrying capacity; in this work, B_c is the point where the tangent to the curve, made by B with respect to the variation of strain ($\partial B(\rho, \epsilon)/\partial \epsilon$), is zero. B_{ip} denotes the BDE density corresponding to the onset of damage in the material. It is estimated as the BDE density at the elastic limit of the material from the MD simulation stress-strain curves

$$B_{ip} = B(\epsilon^i \left| \frac{\partial^2 \sigma}{\partial \epsilon^2} \right|_{>0}, \rho) \quad (3)$$

The BDE density required to initiate plasticity is the critical value at which the second differential of the stress-strain curve exceeds zero ($\partial^2 \sigma / \partial \epsilon^2 > 0$). At the continuum level, an anisotropic damage tensor is introduced which can be simplistically defined along the principal directions, as shown in Equation 4; d_i is the damage parameter defined at the i^{th} principal direction calculated as a function of the weight fraction of CNT and the principal strain along the i^{th} direction at the current time step.

$$D_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} d_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & d_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & d_3 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

The principle of strain equivalence, as shown by Voyiadjis [14] and Shojaei [13], is used to formulate Equations 5 and 6 that define the degraded elastic material properties as a function of the damage parameters. \bar{E}_i and $\bar{\nu}_i$ are the ‘softened’ or damaged material properties whereas E_p and ν_p represent the pristine material properties of the CNT-enhanced epoxy system.

$$\bar{E}_i = E_p (1 - d_i) \quad (5)$$

$$\bar{\nu}_i = \nu_p \left(1 + d_i \left(\frac{0.5}{\nu_p} - 1 \right) \right) \quad (6)$$

The softened material properties are further employed to formulate the kinematics and update the material constitutive equations. For the damaged material, the stress-strain relationship can be described by $\{\sigma_d\} = [\bar{C}]\{\epsilon\}$, where $[\bar{C}]$ is the damaged stiffness tensor developed based on Equations 5 and 6. The constitutive equations in terms of the residual strain and the applied strain can be written as shown in Equation 7. The total strain (ϵ) is defined as the sum of elastic strain (ϵ_e) and damaged or residual strain (ϵ_r).

$$\{\sigma_d\} = [\bar{C}](\{\epsilon\} - \{\epsilon_r\}) \quad (7)$$

A relation for the residual strain is obtained as a function of the undamaged and damaged stiffness tensors and the pristine Cauchy stress tensor, as follows.

$$\{\epsilon_r\} = [C^{-1}]([C] - [\bar{C}])[C^{-1}]\{\sigma_p\} \quad (8)$$

Using the relation in Equation 8, the residual strain is calculated for each time step. The damage energy density (BDE density) from the MD simulation is thus used to develop a damage initiation and evolution law at the continuum scale.

Each unit cell in the stochastic microscale continuum model contains an epoxy matrix cubic element. A representative volume element (RVE) for the model is generated by organizing multiple unit cells in a three dimensional (3D) array. By adopting a stochastic approach to the estimation of matrix properties, each epoxy cubic element of the RVE is characterized by unique material properties, thus, taking into account the local variations in the CNT weight fraction using the probability distributions obtained from MD simulations. The stochastic microscale model and the corresponding sampling methods employed to characterize the stochasticity are explained in detail in Ref [5]. Figure

5 illustrates a 3D volume containing 1000 epoxy matrix sections (i.e., RVE with $10 \times 10 \times 10$ unit cells) when the uncertainty in CNT weight fraction in the epoxy matrix is considered.

Figure 5: (a) RVE in the stochastic microscale continuum model (b) sampled CNT weight fraction values for each section

The CDM equations are integrated into the stochastic microscale model to evaluate the damage and subsequent failure of the microscale RVE under uniaxial tensile loading. The normalized damage parameter for each epoxy section varies between 0 (pristine) to 1 (fully damaged). Figures 6 (a) and (b) show the damage parameters and the stress-strain curve calculated for an RVE when the stochastic microscale model with the CDM formulation is implemented with a mean CNT weight fraction of 2%, 3%, and 4%. It is evident that the RVE exhibits nonlinear behavior at low strains, indicating the presence of plasticity. The damage parameter increases steeply until a critical strain of 15% is reached, followed by a flattening trend. It is important to note that in general epoxy polymers fail at much lower strains during experiments. This is due to the presence of voids and other defects which are not included in this analysis. The increase in CNT weight fraction improves the elastic and inelastic properties of the nanopolymer, as seen from the stress-strain curves; however, the critical strain for damage rate increase remains unchanged. Thus, it is reasonable to conclude that the initiation of damage is more closely attributed to the matrix properties than the inclusion of CNTs.

Figure 6: (a) damage parameter values of microscale RVE (b) Stress-strain curves for microscale RVE

6 CONCLUSION

A novel numerical methodology was developed to replace the physics-based QC method for simulating bond breakage and damage initiation in amorphous polymeric systems with dispersed CNTs. The study primarily addressed the effects of temperature-induced bond vibrations on the molecular system during deformation simulations. It was evident that bond vibrations led to relaxation of bonds and reduced the probability of bond dissociation during tensile simulations. An alternative

technique to the QC method was developed that enables the study of bond dissociation by decoupling the effects of temperature and strain. The MD simulations at near-zero temperatures revealed that temperature also causes an indirect increase in potential energy by inducing geometric distortions to molecular structure. Additionally, the effects of temperature and strain on the variation in potential energy were quantified and decoupled by exploring high strain rate ranges for MD simulations. The tensile deformation simulations performed using a combination of low temperature (~ 1 K) and high strain rate ($\sim 10^{13}$) offer significant computational advantages over the computationally rigorous QC method. The methodology provides a platform to observe bond breakage and quantify the BDE in the molecular system.

The existing CDM method was modified to account for atomistically obtained BDE data. A stochastic microscale continuum model was implemented based on CDM using the BDE density obtained at the nanoscale. The damage parameter in the continuum model was defined based on the energy dissipated in the amorphous molecular system from the elongation and subsequent dissociation of bonds. The stochastic microscale model captured the effects of local variations on the overall inelastic response and damage initiation in the nanopolymer. Results indicate that the inclusion of CNTs improves the overall mechanical response of the nanopolymer; however, the damage initiation phenomenon in CNT-enhanced epoxy polymers is primarily driven by the physics and chemistry of the polymer arising from a fundamental level due to the elongation and dissociation of covalent bonds.

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